

DEVELOPMENT OF CONCENTRATION IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The article discusses the development of concentration skills in preschool children, pedagogical technologies for developing children's concentration skills.

Keywords: concentration, development of skills, educator, pupil, intellectual abilities, creative abilities, children.

INTRODUCTION

Preschool children, in accordance with the State Educational Standards, must acquire the following general important competencies: communicative, game, social, cognitive competencies. The acquisition of these competencies is considered as a result of the child's age, social, physical and mental development process. Concentration is of great importance in this development process, and the volume of scientific research on this topic is expanding. In practical terms, the increase in methods for developing, diagnosing, and assessing a child's concentration is reflected in the impact on children of the social environment in which children live, the modernization of society, and globalization processes. The issue of concentration occupies a special place in the professional activities of the general public, educators, doctors, parents, and all those involved in child-related activities.

Very often, in a fit of rage, parents can't stand it and overwhelm a small child with reproaches and accusations of absent-mindedness and forgetfulness. Remember how often you hear the following cries addressed to the child: "What's going on in your head?", "How can you be such a gaper?", "Are you in the clouds again?"

Indeed, a child almost every day has to hear such complaints addressed to him. An adult believes that a preschooler does not know how to direct his attention to the required goal. Therefore, quite often moms and dads "diagnose" their child as absent-minded.

This situation should be analyzed. You can understand the essence of the problem by speaking out all your complaints to the child, but not out loud. Did it work? The answer to the question is very close and after such an experiment it becomes absolutely obvious. The child can concentrate, but his attention is focused on what is important to him, and not to an adult.

Attention is a mental process that consists of selecting the necessary information in a specific situation and completely rejecting unnecessary information. The point is that external attention is aimed at objects, personalities, phenomena surrounding a person, as well as the actions of other people and changes. A child has this feature from the first days of life. A newborn reacts to the voice of relatives, turns his head towards the source of noise, concentrates attention on relatives.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The attention of small children, aged 3 to 6 years, is focused on their experiences and feelings in the inner world. The maximum concentration of the child's internal attention is achieved at the moment when the child seems to freeze and concentrates on some object, but as if not seeing it. At such moments, the child does not react to the reproaches of adults, does not hear the speech addressed to him. It is these situations that adults call absent-mindedness.

Types of attention

Psychologists distinguish three types of attention.

1. Involuntary attention does not require the involvement of efforts that cause, fix and maintain it, such a process occurs by itself. Often such attention is caused by vivid experiences, noisy events. Interest quickly arises, but also quickly

disappears. Since the object that provoked such interest very quickly becomes ordinary and understandable. Thus, involuntary attention disappears.

2. Voluntary attention is a type of attention that is especially important when the child is not doing what he wants, but performing those actions or tasks that are necessary. Often children give up their favorite or simply interesting activity for the sake of completing a necessary task. Psychologists directly link the level of speech development of children from 3 to 7 years old with the successful formation of this type of attention.

3. Post-voluntary attention is a type of mental process that is formed from voluntary attention and combines the qualities and main characteristics of the previous two types. This occurs at the stage when the preschooler is completely carried away by a game element or a task that interests him. The child does not make special efforts to concentrate on the process of execution. Thus, the child exhibits post-voluntary attention.

Attention: basic properties

The main qualities and characteristics of preschoolers' attention include: concentration, switchability, volume, stability, selectivity, distribution.

Concentration of attention is the ability to quickly focus on an object, as well as to hold attention on the object as much as possible, without succumbing to distracting factors.

Concentration of attention in preschool children is quite low, so you should work on its development. To achieve this goal, you need to choose the right exercises. You can develop the necessary level of attention and its properties by enrolling your child in courses to prepare children for school.

Exercise to improve concentration. You should try to learn short poems with your child. The first part of the poem should be learned with the TV on. The volume should be minimal. Learn the second quatrain with your child while the radio, TV or other source is louder. You should try to learn the final part of the poem by

turning on the TV quite loudly.

Switchability is a property of attention, which consists in the ability to concentrate on one and then a completely different object or activity as quickly as possible. It should be remembered that a small child feels and often demonstrates discontent and tension with his behavior during such a change. The older the child becomes, the less pronounced this feature is.

The scope of attention can be characterized by checking the number of objects that remain in the field of vision and which the child follows. At 5-6 years old, a child simultaneously accompanies and keeps three or more objects in the field of vision. The child's attention at this age is more developed, and he notices quite small details. Whereas at 4 years old, he is able to follow only one object. Keep in mind that if the child sees an object for the first time, the attention span becomes significantly narrower. The difference is also evident in the external characteristics of images. If at 3 years old a child pays attention to the bright features of objects, sizes, then at an older age such qualities become less important.

Stability lies in the duration of the period of concentration of attention on an object or type of activity. Psychologists believe that children of 5 years old can concentrate on a process for up to 2 hours. If it is an interesting and entertaining game, the child can hold attention longer, and much less with a boring activity.

Selectivity of attention allows a preschooler to concentrate on a more important process or object or on a separate stage of the action, which is necessary to solve the task.

Distribution of attention is a feature due to which preschool children can successfully follow several objects or cope with several tasks at the same time.

According to research, rational and rapid distribution of attention requires additional development, training. It is this feature that you should take into account when working with children. It is important to study the individual qualities and characteristics of the child and not forget about them in the process of working with

the child. Don't try to achieve the impossible.

It is necessary to select the necessary exercises and activities for preschoolers to ensure the gradual development of attention without causing any special worries. It is necessary to focus on children's curiosity, as well as individual thinking, which will be especially useful in the learning process.

Human intelligence has many sides - memory and memorization, logical and creative thinking, the ability to analyze and draw conclusions based on any information. It is these abilities that parents try to develop in their children in order to prepare them for further studies at school. But there is another skill that is simply necessary for productive learning in the first grade. We are talking about concentration, which can and should be developed even in preschool age.

It is attention that allows a person to focus both on the educational process and on any other type of activity. A concentrated child or adult perceives information better, since he is not distracted and does not miss important details. All this allows you to more effectively absorb knowledge and spend less time mastering any material.

Like any other area of intelligence, the ability to maintain concentration must be trained. But when it comes to developing attention in children aged 6-7, it is necessary to take into account the age characteristics of the child in order to choose the right educational games and exercises. Let's talk about the nuances that parents must take into account.

Attention in preschool children

At preschool age, it is difficult for children to concentrate on any one process: they are constantly distracted, switching to new, more interesting activities. Parents rarely manage to captivate children for a long time: as a rule, after a few minutes of doing educational tasks, they lose interest in what is happening. Because of this, the process of preparing for school takes so much time, requiring a lot of effort and patience from parents.

One of the reasons why it is difficult for a child to concentrate is his mobility. At 6-7 years old, children are in dire need of physical activity: they are full of energy, they want to run, jump, have fun, and not do any complex and boring exercises. Therefore, training any skill, including attention, should take place in the format of a game in order to make the activities not only useful, but also exciting for the child.

To do this, it is important to select a variety of exercises. You can do it not only at home, but also outside, because many educational games for children involve physical activity. Let's look at several tasks that will help improve the concentration of preschoolers and have fun with the whole family.

Games and exercises

There are a number of tasks aimed at developing the concentration of preschoolers and primary school children. Some of the most effective are the following games and exercises:

- Exercise "Associations". The parent names any word, and the child must come up with an association to it. This is a kind of game in which whole chains of interconnected words are born.

- Game "Forbidden Movement". The parent chooses a movement or gesture that he declares forbidden. For example, a pose with arms raised up was forbidden. Now the parent shows various movements, and the children must repeat all of them, but except for the one that was announced at the beginning.

- Game "Ear-nose". The leader names a part of the body, and the players must not get confused and quickly touch it on themselves. This fun game develops not only attentiveness, but also reaction speed.

- Edible-Inedible Game For this game you will need a ball and a small group. The players line up, and the leader throws a ball to each of them in turn, calling out a word. If the voiced word refers to food, the player must catch the ball with his hands, and if not, then push it away.

- Counting exercises. Not only games, but also various exercises are great for developing attentiveness. So you can ask a preschooler to count from one to ten, and then vice versa. If the baby already knows how to count well, then you can offer him more complex versions of this task: counting by tens or by even numbers.

- Exercises for developing memory and attentiveness. You can offer the following game: lay out several different objects on the table, let the baby remember them well, and then remove them. After that, ask how many objects of a certain color and shape there were.

The listed exercises and games can help in developing attentiveness in children. But will they be enough for a full-fledged concentration training?

Methods for developing attention

Not only attentiveness, but also the memory of children must be trained, because both of these areas of intelligence are aimed at productive acquisition of knowledge. Educational games on the street and at home do not always cope with this task, being more like additional training than a full-fledged set of exercises. In order for classes to bring visible results, they must follow a certain program that consistently improves abilities. It is not always possible to achieve this at home, so most parents prefer to develop their children's skills in additional development centers, where training is conducted under the guidance of an experienced trainer.

Memorika is a comprehensive method for developing children's memory and attention, which has proven its effectiveness in the example of many students. Using elements of play in training allows kids to study with interest and better absorb the material. The acquired skills will become an excellent basis for both school and adult life, because they will remain forever and will help to achieve success in any endeavor more than once.

CONCLUSIONS

A lot of time should be devoted to developing a child's attentiveness, but

according to the recommendations, training in the distribution of attention should be done in a humorous, playful manner. After all, the game, in addition to the fact that it pleases and attracts children, brings them great benefits.

We have described simple ways to develop attentiveness in a child, which you can do on your own. However, it is important to trust the upbringing of your child to children's development centers. Highly qualified specialists of our children's development centers will select a special approach to each child. We conduct both general educational classes and specialized ones. All classes with children are based on the experience of psychology and pedagogy. Although the main ingredient, of course, is unconditional love for children.

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